

Urkun (Exodus) August-September of the 1916*

Legend

- Uezd center
- Russian refugees gathering place
- Local refugees gathering place
- Pass
- Movement of punitive squads
- Movement of local refugees
- Movement of Russian refugees
- State border

* Dates according to pre-revolutionary calendar

** Aksu (84000) Number of local refugees

*** Tashkent (3380) Number of people in the punitive squad

